

Towards Polyvocal Metadata Collection for Colonial Collections: a Pilot Study in Kuching, Malaysia

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Colonial collections in museums are often the result of historical power imbalances, extraction or even violent appropriation (Bennet, 1995). Existing museum metadata thus frequently reflects colonial biases, prioritising documentation and retrieval over perspectives on use, care, and cultural significance. Colonial narratives themselves systematically erase the voices of colonised peoples, creating monolithic accounts that exclude the perspectives and knowledge of source communities (Bon et al. 2022). Even within source communities, different ethnicities and cultural backgrounds exist, yet these are often treated as vague or homogeneous categories.

This pilot study instigated how local knowledge from source communities can enrich colonial collection metadata. We conducted fieldwork in Kuching, Sarawak, a culturally diverse region of Malaysia home to multiple ethnic groups including Iban, Bidayuh, Melanau, Dayak, Malay, and Chinese communities, to gather contemporary perspectives on objects and photographs from the Wereldmuseum Leiden and documented in the Colonial Collections Datahub¹. The Datahub offers the opportunity for anyone to add their own narrative to the metadata and description of objects held in the collection. We selected ten objects and two photographs from 412 Sarawak related records in the collection. We chose a variety of object types as well as level of documentation ranging from no description (e.g. Longhouse photograph²) to extensive documentation from several sources (e.g. Baby carrier³).

Figure 1: Baby carrier from Sarawak held in the Collection of the Wereldmuseum Leiden⁴

Thirteen participants completed the survey in English. Participants were from a variety of cultures present in Kuching: Iban, Bidayuh, Melanau, Dayak, Malay, and Chinese. Some participants were from backgrounds that mixed several of the groups e.g. Chinese, Malay, Iban, and Dayak. Participants were predominantly male with ages ranging from 20 to 65

¹ <https://www.colonialcollections.nl/>

² <https://collectie.wereldmuseum.nl/#/query/8ebbf91f-820b-4c72-bf55-756d9796c877>

³ <https://collectie.wereldmuseum.nl/#/query/5724d2eb-ebe8-4486-a3ba-c2484d19b67c>

⁴ <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11840/810027>

years. Self-assessed familiarity with cultural heritage objects varied considerably (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Self-reported cultural familiarity of the participants.

For each object, participants were asked four questions: one multiple choice about familiarity, and three open-ended questions asking what the respondent saw, what the object was for, and how it should be cared for. The open questions were taken from Maronic's (2024) work on crowd-sourcing for colonial cultural heritage object annotation.

Participant responses revealed significant knowledge variation both across and within cultural groups. The average knowledge (5: very familiar - 1: Not familiar at all) per object was 3.3, ranging from 1.83 to 4.5 per object. The object descriptions often only consisted of the name of the object, the photos and the question about the purpose of the object elicited slightly longer responses. In post survey questions, some participants expressed humility about their limited knowledge, with one noting the challenge of Sarawak's nearly 30 ethnic groups. Several emphasised generational knowledge loss, stating that accurate information requires consulting elders rather than younger "modernised" generations. Participants stressed that single objects may hold different significance across tribes, making universal descriptions problematic.

This pilot demonstrates that scaling up requires targeted recruitment of knowledge holders from specific communities in combination with general local participation. Elicitation methods should encourage longer, detailed responses beyond the brief answers typically received.

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